

12th-13th c Cistercians

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Entry tags: Medieval Christianity, Christian Traditions, Catholic, Religion

The Cistercians are a Catholic religious order, following the Rule of St Benedict. The Order was founded in 1198 in Burgundy (France).

Date Range: 1198 CE - 1250 CE

Region: Europe

Region tags: Europe

Europe

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Yarrow, S., 'Miracles, Belief and Christian Materiality: Relic'ing in Twelfth-Century Miracle Narratives', M. M. Mesley and L. E. Wilson (eds.) *Contextualising Miracles in the Christian West, 1100-1500* (Oxford, 2014), pp. 41-62.
- Source 2: Walker Bynum, C. *Christian Materiality: An Essay on Late Medieval Religion* (Brooklyn, 2011).
- Source 3: Vauchez, A., *Sainthood in the Later Middle Ages*, (trans.) J. Birrell (Cambridge, [1988] 1997).
- Source 1: Bredero, A. H., *Bernard of Clairvaux: Between Cult and History* (Edinburgh, 1996).
- Source 2: *The New Monastery: Texts and Studies on the Early Cistercians* (Kalamazoo, 1998).
- Source 3: Newman, M., *The Boundaries of Charity: Cistercian Culture and Ecclesiastical Reform, 1098-1180* (Stanford, 1996).
- Source 1: Conrad of Eberbach, *Exordium magnum cisterciense sive narration de initio cisterciensis ordinis auctore Conrado*, (ed.) B. Griesser (Rome, 1961; rpt. Turnhout)
- Source 2: Geoffrey of Auxerre, *The First Life of Bernard of Clairvaux* (trans.) H. Costello (Kalamazoo, MI, 2015).
- Source 3: *Herbert of Clairvaux Liber Visionum et Miraculorum Clarevallensium*, (eds.) G. Fois, S. Mula, C. Zichi (Turnhout, 2017).
- Source 1: *S. Bernardi Opera 8 Vols* (eds) J. Leclercq and H. Rochais (Rome, 1957-77).
- Source 2: *The Great Beginning of Cîteaux: A Narrative of the Beginning of the Cistercian Order. The Exordium Magnum of Conrad of Eberbach*. (Trans. B. Ward and P. Savage, Ed. E. R. Elder) (Collegeville, MN, 2012).
- Source 3: Waddell, C., *Twelfth-Century Statutes from the Cistercian General Chapter. Latin text with English Notes and Commentary*. (Studia et Documenta 12. Cistercian: Commentarii Cistercienses. Kalamazoo, 2002).

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://www.cchahistory.ca/journal/CCHA1968/Desmond.html>
- Source 1 Description: Desmond, L.A. 'Becket and the Cistercians', CCHA, Study Sessions, 35 (1968).
- Source 2 URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1111/j.1478-0542.2010.00709.x>
- Source 2 Description: Mula, S. 'Twelfth- and Thirteenth-Century Cistercian Exempla Collections: Role, Diffusion, and Evolution', History Compass, 8 (2010) pp. 903–912.
- Source 3 URL: <http://gahom.ehess.fr/index.php?434>
- Source 3 Description: International Bibliography of exempla examples

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <http://gahom.ehess.fr/index.php?434>
- Source 1 Description: International Bibliography of exempla examples
- Source 2 URL: <http://betula.annexus.ehess.fr/sdx/cesaire/index.xsp>
- Source 2 Description: The Latin edition of the Dialogus miraculorum by Cistercian Caesarius of Heisterbach, an important work written in the first half of the thirteenth century (in the 1220s) and published in two volumes by Joseph Strange in 1851.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– Yes

Notes: Insofar as particular groups of people were more likely to become monks

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– Yes

Notes: Cistercians did not accept child oblates

↳ Assigned by gender:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– I don't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: Individual Cistercian abbots preached in the Midi, Gascony, Germany, and the Holy Land. They preached against heresy and to recruit for the crusades.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:

– Yes

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

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↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The General Chapter The abbot at the head of each filiation

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: Some abbots were venerated as saints

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The General Chapter was responsible for issuing statutes.

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– I don't know

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– I don't know

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– I don't know

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳

How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (rare)

Notes: When travelling to the General Chapter or on monastery business, monks may take the opportunity to venerate important shrines. However, stability in the monastery was important, and pilgrimage to the Holy Land for example was discouraged. Openness to lay pilgrims in Cistercian monasteries varied between communities.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:
– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:
– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:
– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:
– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:
– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:
– No

↳ Mummification:
– No

↳ Interment:
– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):
– No

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):
– Yes

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: Remains could be translated if necessitated by building work or signs of sanctity

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Notes: Lay patrons could be interred in family groups in Cistercian precincts

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Abbots may be buried in the chapter house or cloister walk

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: There are exempla and hagiographic accounts of visions of deceased brethren and saints.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ Through divination processes:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Visions of angels and demons

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it

relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:
Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:
– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s):
– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: A saint's intercession was through the power of God

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– I don't know

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - No
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - No
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - Yes
 - Notes: In the context of Cistercian participation in the Crusades, for example.
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Visions of God or the saints, tasting sweetness when taking communion
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

- ↳ Courage (in battle):
 - No
- ↳ Courage (generic):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - Yes

- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - No
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - Yes
 - Notes: Sufficient to undertake the necessary manual labour
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - No
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - No
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: The Cistercians followed a strict, austere diet. There were periods of fasting in accordance with the Catholic calendar, and occasionally as punishment.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular

Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized

way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– No

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

↳ Hair:

– Yes

↳ Dress:

– Yes

↳ Ornaments:

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: Individual monasteries provided famine relief and charity for their local communities on occasion

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: Individual monasteries provided famine relief and charity for their local communities on occasion

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: Elderly or ill monks would be placed in the infirmary.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– Yes

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: The place of nuns in Cistercian history is contentious. For further reading see: Constance

H. Berman, 'Were There Twelfth-Century Cistercian Nuns?', *Church History*, Vol. 68, No. 4 (Dec., 1999), pp. 824-864 Elizabeth Freeman, 'Cistercian Nuns in Medieval England: The gendering of geographic marginalisation', Online <https://ir.uiowa.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1003&context=mff>

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The Cistercians did not accept child oblates into the Order; recruits may have attended school or university prior to joining.

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– I don't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Notes: Individual monasteries could provide famine relief to their local communities

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Notes: See for example Byland Abbey: <https://historicengland.org.uk/listing/the-list/list-entry/1013403>

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: Monasteries were expected to contribute to the running costs of the General Chapter

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Cistercians were notably exempt from papal tithes. This was a source of tension, especially when special taxes (such as to finance crusade ventures) were raised

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Notes: Disputes could be discussed and settled at the General Chapter/ the Chapter could decide on arbiters

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: See Narrative and legislative texts from early Cîteaux. Edited by Chrysogonus Waddell. (*Studia et Documenta*, 9.)

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided

by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Patoralism